

FEATURES OF TURNING PAIN INTO A TRAGEDY IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHOSOMATIC DISEASES

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Annotation. The article provided information on chronic pain and analyzed the degree to which patients with psychosomatic disease can turn pain into a tragedy. In Psychosomatic patients, the characteristics of turning pain into tragedy are reflected in three different approaches, such as indulgence in imagination, exaggeration and helplessness.

Keywords: pain, psychosomatics, psychosomatic disorders, nosology, perceptive, vegetative, motor, cognitive, emotional – affective, psychological characteristics, indulgence in fantasies, exaggeration, helplessness.

The phenomenon of chronic pain has been studied by scientists for many years. Because chronic pain incorporates into the clinical manifestations of many diseases, one of the main human complaints (occurs up to 15-70%) is counted. We can see an increasing relevance with the number of scientific publications dedicated to this problem, international regional congresses, specialized clinics and conferences dedicated to the study of pain.

In the last years, chronic pain began to acquire the status of not only a syndrome, but also a nosology. Chronic pain is seen as a psychosomatic disorder in a number of studies. There is a need to change the conceptual approach to the concept of chronic pain not as a symptom of a disease, but as an independent pathological process or disease. According to this idea, pain is a multicomponent formation, and it includes the following – perceptive (perception of the place of harm), vegetative (sympathy adrenal system, reflecting reflexive changes in the work of internal organs and tone), motor (aimed at eliminating the influence of damaging stimuli), cognitive (attitude to pain and interpretation of pain based on the currently organized preference) and emotional-affective (unpleasant psycho-emotional anxiety). Within the framework of the bio psychosocial model of diseases, chronic pain is considered as a state of somatic disease of a person who has a certain set of personal characteristics and appears under the influence of a certain family and socio-cultural context.

In patients with psychosomatic diseases, we studied the features of turning pain into a tragedy, which is reflected in three different approaches, which make up a total of one tragic indicator.

The first approach focuses a person's attention on thoughts related to pain, and the first scale of the methodology – "mental gum" - that is, the mind serves as the basis for succumbing to delusions.

The second approach has been found to be the tendency of some people to exaggerate the strength, importance and consequences of pain, and serves as the basis for distinguishing the second scale of the methodology - exaggeration.

The third approach emphasizes the adoption of the position of modesty, helplessness and inability to control the situation when pain appears, and serves as the basis for the third scale of the methodology – despair, helplessness, helplessness.

All three scales are moderately interconnected, which allows us to consider them as different components of one basic structure.

Table 1.

Results of studies of the properties of turning pain into a tragedy in patients with psychosomatic diseases (Kruskal-Wallis H-criterion)

Pointers	Ischemic heart disease (n=191)	diabetes mellitus	Bronchial asthma	gastrointestinal ulcer disease (n=64)	rheumatoid arthritis (n=93)	Control Group (n=48)	H	P
The degree of turning pain into tragedy	423,8	332,7	283,7	403,9	338,2	136,2	100,41	0,000*
Indulging in imagination	426,3	329,3	287,9	350,1	338,8	200,6	68,52	0,000*
Exaggeration	383,8	332,8	337,3	412,2	343,7	153,0	61,42	0,000*
Helplessness	364,8	374,3	285,0	421,0	348,1	161,3	67,15	0,000*

Note: * - $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$

In our study, the results of the characteristics of turning patients with psychosomatic diseases into pain tragedies are given in Table 1.

The results of the study show that patients suffering from gastrointestinal ulcer diseases and ischemic heart diseases have a higher level of transformation of pain into a disaster comparing to other diseases ($H=423.8$; $p<0.01$), while these patients overthink about their disease. the index of fantasy is high ($H=426.3$). Hence, patients with gastrointestinal ulcer diseases and ischemic heart disease are given constant thoughts about the pain they feel.

In conclusion, patients with psychosomatic diseases have a higher rate of turning pain into a tragedy compared to other non-chronic diseases. Therefore, psychodiagnostics should be performed on patients with psychosomatic diseases and the methods of psychocorrection should be used depending on the detected changes.

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